

Multilevel Thoracic Spinal Epidural Hematoma: Emergency Surgery or Conservative Treatment? A Rare Case Report

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Abstract

Background. Spinal epidural hematoma is a rare condition that can occur either spontaneously or as a result of trauma. The causes and factors influencing outcomes remain controversial. Rapid diagnosis and surgical evacuation of the hematoma are critical for effective treatment.

Study design. A case report

Case presentation. A 78-year-old female patient was hospitalized with complaints of knee pain. Two days after the patient's prosthesis surgery, acute paraplegia was detected in the lower extremity during the mobilization process. In the thoracic magnetic resonance images, a compression fracture in the middle and anterior part of the T4 vertebral body and a spinal epidural hematoma extending from the T4 vertebral level to the L1 vertebral level was detected and urgent decompressive laminectomy was performed. Postoperative 24-hour, first-month, and sixth-month follow-ups were performed and motor recovery was observed. She was seen swimming and walking without any help.

Conclusion. Although the management of spinal epidural hematoma cases affecting one or more levels is controversial in the literature, the time between the onset of neurological symptoms and surgical decompression is an important factor affecting surgical outcomes. In this case, we discuss a case of massive thoracic spinal epidural hematoma caused by anticoagulant use, increased intra-abdominal pressure during early mobilization, random compression fracture, and vascular injury due to epidural spinal anesthesia.

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Background

Spinal epidural hematomas (SEHs) are not common, they require early diagnosis and urgent surgical treatment. Spinal epidural hematoma may occur in 0.1-0.24% as an unexpected complication of surgical procedures or simply with lumbar epidural puncture [1,2]. According to the literature, the cause of hematoma in the epidural space may be idiopathic or spontaneous as a result of minor trauma without a

vertebral fracture. Traumatic spinal epidural hematomas are seen in 0.5-1.7% of all spinal cord traumas. Spontaneous epidural hematomas are seen in 40% of all epidural bleeding [3,4].

Spinal fractures most commonly occur in the thoracolumbar region of the spine. These fractures typically result from high-energy trauma in younger individuals. However, older adults can also be caused

by lower-energy trauma due to osteoporosis and age-related changes in the spine [5].

Our patient had a history of falling, was prepared with epidural spinal anesthesia during knee prosthesis surgery, and used anticoagulant, When acute paraplegia developed a thoracic vertebra MRI revealed an incidental T4 compression fracture and an invasive epidural hematoma starting from the proximal T4 vertebral level and extending to the back of the T12 vertebral body, and emergency extensive decompressive thoracic laminectomy was detected. This case is presented because there are spontaneous and traumatic causes such as anticoagulant use, spinal anesthesia, and old compression fracture that caused thoracic invasive SEH.

Case Presentation

A 78-year-old female patient was admitted to the hospital with complaints of knee pain. The patient, who underwent bilateral knee replacement surgery, could

move on the first day. However, sudden paralysis occurred on the second day in the lower half of her body. The patient's neurological examination revealed that paraplegia had developed and that there was a progressive loss of strength in the left lower extremity at 0/5, and in the right lower extremity at 1/5 (there is contraction, but no extremity movement). After consulting with the hematology department, the patient received 2 units of erythrocyte transfusion, 2 units of fresh frozen plasma (FFP), and 2 units of pooled platelet transfusion. This was due to the preoperative hematological test results, which showed a complete blood count(CBC) of 7.8 g/dl and a platelet value of 126000. In the MRI, an incidental compression fracture in the middle and anterior part of the T4 vertebra and a 1 cm thick epidural hematoma extending from T4 to L1 vertebrae, compressing the spinal cord were detected (Figure 1 a,b,c,d).

Figure 1: Emergency Preoperative Thoracic Vertebra MRIs After Acute Paraplegia:
a-b. sagittal and axial sections of the T4 level in T2-weighted images;

c-d. Epidural hematoma extending into the lower posterior of the T12 vertebra on T2-weighted sagittal and axial images

Surgical Management

The patient was prepared for the operating table in the prone position under general anesthesia. Preoperative records were obtained with intraoperative neuromonitoring (IONM). The subcutaneous tissues were cut with a midline skin incision between the T3/L1 spinous processes and the bilateral paravertebral

muscles were stripped subperiosteal. Decompressive laminectomy covering the T4-L1 vertebral levels (9 levels) was performed. The hematoma was successfully removed during surgery and since the spinal joints were intact, the pressure on the spinal cord was eliminated without additional support (Figure 2 a).

**Figure 2. a-Macroscopically, in Operation, Epidural Hematoma Compressing the Dorsal of the Thoracic Spinal Cord
b- Histopathology of Postoperative Spinal Epidural Hematoma**

The pathology result reported findings compatible with hematoma containing erythrocytes, fibrin, and blood elements (Figure 2 b). During the operation, cord pulsation was observed to return. With IONM, the patient's neurological findings were monitored using somatosensory evoked potentials (SSEP), muscle MEP, spontaneous EMG monitoring, and an increase in the lower extremity values. At the beginning of the spinal

surgery, the patient was administered 4x4 mg IV Dexamethasone. The patient's medical history included a fall two years ago, diabetes mellitus, and ischemic heart disease. Additionally, the patient had combined epidural-spinal anesthesia and received two doses of Clexane 6000 IU subcutaneously on the first day of the prosthesis surgery.

**Figure 3: a- Acute Paraplegia Developed Two Days After Knee Prosthesis Surgery in Case
b-Mobilization of the Case with Bilateral Cane Support at the Postoperative First Month
c- the Patient's Ability to Walk Comfortably without a Cane or Personal Support at 6 Months Postoperatively**

In the follow-up for the patient; the first postoperative day showed a 4/5 strength loss in the dorsiflexion of the right foot and toes and a 1/5 strength loss in the dorsiflexion of the left foot and toes. However, motor recovery began in the lower extremities. After 2 weeks post-surgery, the patient was discharged, able to stand

and take steps with the support of another person. In the first month after surgery, the patient could walk with the support of two canes. By the 6th month, she could walk without any support (Figure 3 a,b,c). MRIs conducted one month and six months post-surgery revealed no spinal canal bleeding (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Six Months After the Surgery, the Thoracal Vertebra MRIs a-b. Showed No Signs of Bleeding in the Spinal Canal

An informed consent form and permission to share pictures were obtained from the patient.

Discussion

Spinal epidural hematoma (SEH) is a rare condition that can occur either spontaneously or as a result of trauma. In some patients, it may be difficult to determine the cause of epidural bleeding. Pregnancy, increased intra-abdominal and intra-thoracic pressure, coughing, sneezing, vomiting, urination, trauma, and anticoagulant use have been reported to contribute [3,6,7]. In our case, when acute paraplegia developed 2 days after prosthesis surgery, an incidental T4 compression fracture due to a previous fall was detected by early thoracic MRI. During the prosthesis surgery, it was discovered that the epidural-spinal anesthesia catheter was inserted up to the L1 vertebra level. On the first day after the surgery, a small amount of bloody fluid was observed in the catheter line during its removal, and anticoagulant medication was administered twice.

The most frequent post-traumatic fractures in the thoracolumbar region are compression fractures, burst fractures, flexion-distraction injuries, and fracture dislocations, which vary based on their mechanism of formation [5]. The morphology of the fracture encountered in our case is a single end-plate fracture that does not involve the posterior wall of the vertebral body. It defines vertebral body damage without posterior ligament complex (PLC) damage. Again, Chance fractures are also so-called flexion-distraction injuries that occur primarily with rotational forces applied to the spinal middle column from the anterior. The risk of serious neurological damage associated with flexion and distraction is 10-15% [1,2]. Change fractures

are fractures of the thoracic and lumbar vertebrae that develop due to flexion-distraction forces and cause delayed spinal epidural hematoma after trauma. Spinal epidural hematomas (SEH) may develop in 0.5-1.7% of patients with change fractures [8,9]. These fractures may occur in the vertebral bodies, pedicles, spinous processes, and thoracic and thoracolumbar junctions. They are often encountered in traumas when bleeding occurs while using anticoagulants, or acute paraparesis or paraplegia develops, an MRI examination should be performed under emergency conditions and decompressive intervention (with or without fusion) should be performed at the levels where compression occurs [8].

The use of anticoagulants is a significant risk factor in patients with spontaneous spinal epidural hematoma [3]. If unusual focal neurological deficits develop in a patient using anticoagulants and neuroimaging confirms acute bleeding, vitamin K and fresh frozen plasma (FFP) or isolated preparations (II, VII, IX, and X) can be used to stop the bleeding. The causes of spinal epidural hematoma are diverse and multifactorial. Some reports suggest that the cause is hypertension or coagulopathy [10]. Publications have been reported suggesting that it is caused by extra-dural spinal vascular anomaly, and it has been stated that 40% of the underlying causes of this disease are unknown [10,11].

We believe that several factors contributed to the development of acute paraplegia in our case. These factors include coagulopathy due to anticoagulant use, increased intra-abdominal pressure during early mobilization after knee replacement surgery, and iatrogenic spinal catheter application. However, it's

important to note that we did not encounter posterior ligament damage resulting from a T4 compression fracture due to previous trauma during the operation. In the 1990s, Bracken and colleagues reported that high-dose intravenous bolus administration of Methylprednisolone (MP) at 30 mg/kg followed by a maintenance dose of 5.4 mg/kg IV could improve neurological recovery in acute spinal cord injuries (ASCI) [12,13]. Before the onset of paraplegia, an 8 mg dexamethasone IV bolus was given in preparation for emergency decompression. Following surgery, 4 mg dexamethasone IV boluses were administered at 6-hour intervals. Neurological improvement was observed, and the drug administration was stopped shortly after.

The severity and reversibility of spinal cord damage are influenced by multiple factors. The amount, size, and location of bleeding, as well as the duration of cord compression, are the most significant factors. Early relief of cord compression can minimize mechanical, histological, and biochemical damage. Consequently, the time from symptom onset to surgical intervention is a crucial factor affecting the prognosis [14].

Conclusion

In the literature, it has been reported that hematoma in the epidural space can occur idiopathically or develop spontaneously as a result of minor trauma without a vertebral fracture. However, in our case, we observed a massive epidural hematoma due to reasons such as the use of anticoagulants, increased intra-abdominal pressure during early mobilization, a random compression fracture, and vascular injury due to epidural spinal anesthesia. We relieved the pressure on the spinal cord two hours after symptom onset, leading to improved neurological findings and an enhanced quality of life for the patient

Abbreviations

MRI Magnetic resonance imaging
SEH Spinal epidural hematoma
FFP Fresh frozen plasma
IONM Intraoperative neuromonitoring
SSEP Somatosensory evoked potential
MEP Motor evoked potential
PLC Posterior ligament complex
CBC Complete blood count

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Not applicable.

Consent for publication

An informed consent form and permission to share pictures were obtained from the patient or parent

Availability of data and materials

All data generated or analyzed during this study are included in this published article [and its supplementary information files]

Competing interests

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Author contributions

The corresponding author participated in the data collection and

analysis,

BL did the literature review and wrote the manuscript.

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